

Figure S1. MAE of trained Bouc-wen parameters

Figure S2. RMSE of trained Bouc-wen parameters

Figure S3. MAE of physical validation

Figure S4. RMSE of physical validation

Figure S5. Box plots of Bouc-wen parameters

Supplementary material of: ML-Based Hysteretic Response Prediction of Slender CFST Beam-Column Connections under Bidirectional Loading.
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